

VALKYRIES

D6.3 Roadmap for enhancing the Pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi- casualty disasters

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1. Executive Summary

The goal of deliverable D6.3 is to describe the process and the results from the prioritization of the harmonization opportunities identified in Work Package (WP) 6. This process includes several sequential steps. First, clustering of the opportunities – from the original 57 to 11 clustered based on how close are by meaning. Second, opportunities analysis, which includes rating based on the survey among the VALKYRIES project consortium, creation of opportunities matrix. Third, opportunities ranking. Fourth, identification of interdependences among the top-5 ranked opportunities at the WP6 level and with the ones highly ranked in WP4 and WP5. Fifth, evaluation of top-5 ranked opportunities; and sixth, development of roadmap for implementation of the top-5 ranked opportunities. Finally, the deliverable summarizes the main conclusions from the analyses.

(Common points through deliverables WP4, WP5 and WP6)

Due to the horizontality of the project at this stage and the similarities in work packages 4, 5 and 6, a common work methodology has been established for them. This allows to intercompare results between work packages, to be efficient and to provide a holistic result.

For these reasons a common Table of Content (TOC) has been established for deliverables 4.3, 5.3 and 6.3. Some chapters are common to these deliverables, which is why they are marked in their title as (common).

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Roadmap for enhancing the Pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

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3. Introduction

The aim of the H2020-VALKYRIES project is to develop, integrate and demonstrate capabilities for enabling immediate and coordinated emergency response including search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in which several regions or countries are affected and hence greater interoperability being required.

H2020 - VALKYRIES project will propose harmonization roadmaps of some of the discovered technological (work stream KARA), procedural (work stream HERJA) and collaborative and training (work stream EIR) opportunities.

The WP6 entitled “Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses aims to implement international comparative research on the process of building a harmonisation framework for enhancing the cooperation between first aid responders with other disaster management actors. Besides, it targets improving cooperation between main actors in first aid response to multi casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters in the cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical context.

The goal of this deliverable D6.3, "Roadmap for enhancing the Pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters" is to describe the process of clustering and prioritization of the identified harmonisation opportunities in the deliverables D6.2 (first version) and D6.6 (final version), focusing on the most relevant ones, and to propose EU-wide roadmap for their harmonisation and pre-standardisation.

The first part of the deliverable describes the process of clustering of identified harmonization opportunities in deliverables D6.2 (first version) and D6.6 (final version). The next part presents harmonisation opportunity analysis which is based on the feasibility-impact matrix. The third part focuses on opportunities rating according to the questionnaire. It presents feasibility-impact evaluation of the clustered opportunities as a result of the voting of the VALKYRIES project partners. After that, the ranking of the selected opportunities according to their score is presented and analysed. The following part of the deliverable Identifies and analyses the interdependences among the top-5 high ranking opportunities at the level of the WP6, as well as among W4 and WP5. The next part is devoted to the evaluation of the top-5 ranked opportunities. Finally, the last two parts of D6.3 focus on the roadmap for pre-standardisation of the top-5 harmonisation opportunities and the stake holder's evaluation.

3.1 Objective

The principal objective of the H2020 VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness and cross-sector/border cooperation and education and training for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

3.1.1. Structure criteria Methodology (common)

The methodology for the development of the deliverable D6.3 was commonly agreed among the leaders of WP4, WP5 and WP6 and it is common for deliverables D4.3 and D5.3. NOVOTEC as framework harmonisation and INDRA as project leader supported this process.

The methodology and the structure of this document includes the following sequential steps:

- Taxonomy process
- Clustering of the of identified harmonization opportunities in the deliverables D5.2 (first version) and D5.6 (final version)
- Harmonized analysis of the opportunities, which is based on the feasibility-impact matrix.
- Analysis of the results of the matrix and explanation.
- Opportunities matrix with the results
- Opportunities ranking
- Interdependences with other opportunities
- SWOT analysis
- Roadmap for work package and for opportunity.
- Stakeholders' evaluation
- Conclusions

3.1.2. ID Codification/Traceability (common)

To ensure traceability of gaps, opportunities and grouping of opportunities between WPs. A codification of each of the topics to be addressed has been carried out.

Gaps and opportunities codification

In this deliverable D6.3, the coding of gaps and opportunities established in D6.2 (first version) and D6.6 (final version) is maintained for ease of reading and to establish a link between the different work packages and deliverables of the Project.

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
G=Gap OP= Opportunity	Task number	-	Item number (1..n)
Example			
G	6.1	-	1

Table 1 – ID codification structure for traceability (Gaps and Opportunities)

Clustered Opportunities codification

It has been established a coding for clustered opportunities formed on the basis of the original opportunities. Following the above structure, they are formed according to the following table:

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
CO= Clustered Opportunities	Work package number	-	cluster number (1..n)
Example			
CO	WP5	-	1

Table 2 – ID codification structure for traceability (Clustered Opportunities)

3.2. Exclusion criteria

For the initial analysis and development on this deliverable, all the gaps and harmonisation opportunities identified in deliverable D6.2 (first version) and D6.6 (updated and final version) have been considered. Following the process of clustering and ranking of the grouped opportunities, according to the commonly agreed methodology among WP4, WP5 and WP6

described for the current deliverable, further analysis of focuses on the top 5 opportunities selected after the survey among VALKYRIES partners and the internal discussions in the framework of WP6.

3.3. Experts' consultation (common)

The results of the harmonisation and pre-standardization tasks have been subjected to internal validation processes with the most expert project partners in each case, consultation with the External Advisory Board (EAB) and, in some cases, external validation with experts from outside the project. The results from the survey with WP6 questionnaire are reported in the deliverable D6.5.

4. Taxonomy process (common)

Deliverable D2.2 "Terminology and semantics" provides a unified glossary and a map of joint terminologies and semantic representations focused on the specificities of cross-sectoral, cross-border and cross-hierarchical action against European multi-victim disasters. The objective is to support the harmonization, pre-standardization and standardization efforts of first responders in disasters. Deliverable D2.2 has been based on the proposal, debate, discussion and consensus of the different terms, and has been kept alive during the whole life cycle of the Project, serving as a constant reference for the researchers in their work and in the drafting of the respective deliverables.

Following this consensus, for work on D6.3, the VALKYRIES partners carried out a review of the terminology used in relation to the statements and contents of the opportunities detected to homogenize them. This facilitated not only the grouping of similar opportunities, but also the study of interdependencies between related opportunities inside and outside the WP6, a fundamental aspect in the analysis, prioritization and roadmap for the evolution and adoption of new common practices and procedures for first responder responses in the EU environment.

This process has been carried out in the same way in the development of the works leading to deliverables D4.3, D5.3 and D6.3 of the Project.

5. Clustering opportunities

In the deliverable D6.6 Harmonisation opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters, a total of **57 harmonisation opportunities** were identified because of the work of the partners in WP6.

The VALKYRIES partners analysed in depth all opportunities to evaluate similarities and differences between them to group the opportunities which cover the same issue.

Accordingly, those opportunities that present common aspects were grouped/clustered, generating a new umbrella or clustered opportunity. Thus, a total of 11 umbrella opportunities were defined where each one can be composed of one or more opportunities that are related to each other.

Table 3 shows, in the two left columns, the clustered opportunity with its code and on the right column, the opportunities that were merged into it.

Code of clustered harmonisation opportunities	Clustered harmonisation opportunities	Merged harmonisation opportunities
CO.WP6-1	Common resource federation strategy	OP6.1-1 Use of resource federation techniques; OP6.1-2 Create a common regulation for resource federation at the EU level; OP6.1-3 Dynamic management of data federation; OP6.1-12 EU Regulations regarding data federation framework; OP6.1-13 Definition of general data federation frameworks; OP6.1-14 Federation incompatibilities; OP6.1-15 OAuth 2.0 - Optimised designs for data federations; OP6.1-16 OAuth 2.0 - Redundant authorisation server; OP6.1-17 Shibboleth - Single Sign Out; OP6.1-18 Shibboleth - Reduce implementation complexity; OP6.1-19 PQC KEM hybrid schemas; OP6.1-20 PQC DSA hybrid schemas; OP6.1-21 Quantum Key Distribution; OP6.1-22 Light cryptographic methods; OP6.1-23 Distributed PKI; OP6.1-24 Common data language, taxonomy and reference schema; OP6.1-26 COP marking data source; OP6.1-28 Valkyries framework; OP6.1-29 Information integration; OP6.1-30 Protocol of use and development.

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Code of clustered harmonisation opportunities	Clustered harmonisation opportunities	Merged harmonisation opportunities
CO.WP6-2	Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	OP6.1-4 Use of temporal session keys; OP6.1-5 Generate a certification authority at EU level for emergencies; OP6.1-6 Use of hybrid cryptographic solutions; OP6.1-25 Tampered data.
CO.WP6-3	Use of data redundancy strategies	OP6.1-7 Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data storage; OP6.1-8 Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data coherence; OP6.1-9 EU regulations regarding data redundancy; OP6.1-27 Backup data.
CO.WP6-4	Dynamic resource management, such as network and security capabilities	OP6.1-10 Dynamic network management; OP6.1-11 On-demand security capabilities
CO.WP6-5	Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses	OP6.2-1 Common core curriculum for the specialty of emergency medicine; OP6.2-2 European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur); OP6.2-6 Creation of a universally valid European First Aid Certificates; OP6.2-7 Creation of European register of qualified personnel for the intervention in Multi Casualty Incident (MCI).
CO.WP6-6	Creation of an EU system for Lessons learned and exercises for first aid responses	OP6.5-5 Creation of a UCPM Lessons Learnt data base at the European level; OP6.2-8 Regularly conduct of joint multinational simulation exercises.
CO.WP6-7	Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)	OP6.3-2 Virtual Operation Support Teams
CO.WP6-8	Development and implementation of a Strategy for rising of public awareness in MCI with catalogue of visual warning	OP6.3-3 Debriefing sessions after each incident or disaster; OP6.3-5 Strategy for public awareness; OP6.3-6 Unified communication language; OP6.3-7

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Code of clustered harmonisation opportunities	Clustered harmonisation opportunities	Merged harmonisation opportunities
	signs to alert and inform the population	Improvement of citizens' engagement in crisis management at local level.
CO.WP6-9	Implementation of Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance	OP6.4-1 Implementation of European Civil-Military Doctrine; OP6.4-5 Conduct active outreach to raise awareness of the benefits of military involvement in large-scale cross border disasters; OP6.4-2 Improving of shared interagency understanding by working together, connecting and joint multinational education.
CO.WP6-10	Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions	OP6.4-4 Plans, programs and scenarios for joint training of civil-military teams developing; OP6.4-3 Development of national requirements and capabilities for the implementation of joint civil-military procedures in case of disasters, accidents and catastrophes; OP6.4-6 Introduction of new technology solutions for communications and data exchange.
CO.WP6-11	Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities	OP6.5-1 OP6.5-6 Creation of minimum set of basic competencies and skills for different first aid spontaneous volunteers with unified training program; OP6.5-2 OP6.5-3 OP6.5-4 Integration of volunteers in real field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities.

Table 3 – WP6 Harmonisation opportunities original and merged after the clustering

6. Opportunities analysis

6.1. Methodology (common for WP4, WP5, WP6)

It has been necessary to agree on which the most relevant opportunities in the work packages were. The following approach was commonly agreed and used in the opportunities analysis among the WP4, WP5 and WP6 opportunities and partners.

To reach this agreement, a modified Delphi methodology has been used in which the experts are the consortium partners.

The questionnaire consists of a score from 1 to 10 on 13 questions divided into two groups, feasibility and impact.

The questions within the **feasibility group** are focused on defining how feasible it is to implement the grouped opportunity. Aspects such as the resources or capacities of the system, ethical-legal regulation, technological advances and implementation costs have considered.

Feasibility determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?	8%
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?	17%
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?	17%
Is there technology available to fulfil this opportunity?	17%
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?	17%
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?	7%
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal?	17%

Table 4 – Feasibility evaluated factors and relative percentage assigned

The questions within the **impact group** are focused on defining what the impact of the opportunity would be once implemented. Aspects such as the objective and the target stakeholders for whom it is proposed, or what is expected to happen in the end, must be considered.

Impact determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?	33%
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?	14%
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?	14%
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?	13%
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?	13%
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuations?	13%

Table 5 – Impact evaluated factors and relative percentage assigned

With the answers to the questions and the appropriate weighting, a score will be obtained for each group. One for feasibility and one for impact. In this way, the opportunity can be placed in a matrix format.

The scores have been used as coordinates that replace the opportunity and locate the opportunity in the matrix. This can identify the opportunities with the best relation.

The result of the analysis in each case would fall into one of the following 4 combinations:

- **Low feasibility / Low impact (THANKLESS TASKS):** these are initiatives that are low recommended because they will not be significant for the desired changes in the system. The realization of these initiatives involves a high degree of difficulty for the implementation and the result will not bring a significant improvement.
- **High feasibility / Low impact (FILL-INS):** these are initiatives that can be implemented quickly and in the short term, but the effect they will have on the desired changes will be marginal and insignificant.
- **Low feasibility / High impact (MAJOR PROJECTS):** these are ideas, often disruptive, that are complex to execute. They may require further analysis or follow-up to assess their priority, degree of impact, risks involved in implementing them (or not implementing them), etc.
- **High feasibility / High impact (QUICK WINS):** these are initiatives that can be implemented and executed relatively easily in a short time. They are very valuable because they can generate a significant change in the system.

The feasibility-impact matrix presents the results of the opportunities analysed in a scatter plot where each of the 4 combinations described corresponds to one of the 4 quadrants represented.

Figure 1 – Feasibility-impact matrix quadrants

The feasibility-impact evaluation of the clustered opportunities was done by voting of the VALKYRIES project partners in which each partner in the consortium had one vote. Internally, each partner decided the value of its votes by consensus among its own researchers.

The results of voting for each clustered opportunity, both its feasibility and its impact are presented and visualised in the tables and figures below.

CO.WP6-1: Common resource federation strategy		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity will allow a country to share data (patients, triage, emergency) from databases located in this to other countries. The use of authorization tokens would allow to have data during a certain time, for example, the duration of the emergency.	This opportunity is hard to implement although the technology already exists. However, the time to develop Valkyries project is quite short for a fully implementation of this opportunity because it is necessary to establish a common regulation for data federation at EU level, secure communications and mechanisms, and common unified schemas between the different databases which composed the system. The interoperability mechanisms require that applications to integrate a common federation to comply with the SIGRUN API.
Rating	6,1	5,9

Table 6 – CO.WP6-1: Common resource federation strategy

Figure 2 - Feasibility-impact results: Common resource federation strategy

CO.WP6-2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of cryptographic mechanisms will be ensuring data confidentiality, prevent the data from be accessed from unintentional, unlawful, or unauthorized access, disclosure, or theft.	Due to the large number of cryptographic mechanisms, this opportunity presents a high feasibility score. Moreover, it can be implemented and validated during the time of Valkyries project in the UCs. By default, the communication between application and SIGRUN Core services will be based on secure internet connection (e.g. HTTPS). Finally, it is also easy to implement because terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights will be not considered.
Rating	5,9	6,7

Table 7 – CO.WP6-2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

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FEASIBILITY evaluated aspects		Average
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?		6
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?		6
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?		7
Is there technology available to fulfill this opportunity?		7,5
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?		6
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?		7
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal? VERY IMPORTANT FOR 7.4		7

IMPACT evaluated aspects		Average
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?		4
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?		8
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?		6
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?		6
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?		7
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuations?		7

Figure 3 - Feasibility-impact results: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

CO.WP6-3: Use of data redundancy strategies		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of this opportunity will improve the acquisition of data from multiples database in real-time. Such approach would remove the need to create another database managing the integration with a central data. Furthermore, if one database failed the system would still work.	Due to the technology already available, the implementation is not tough. However, this kind of strategy requires a high knowledge of database systems. VALKYRIES core services support databases replication and clustering, but for cross-country engines rules need to be agreed between countries or at the EU level for databases sync. Additionally, it is necessary to establish a common regulation of data redundancy at the EU level. Therefore, the time for implementation and validation is higher than the time of the project.
Rating	5,7	6,0

Table 8 – CO.WP6-3: Use of data redundancy strategies

FEASIBILITY evaluated aspects		Average
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?		6,5
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?		5
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?		7
Is there technology available to fulfill this opportunity?		7
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?		5
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?		5
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal? VERY IMPORTANT FOR 7.4		6

IMPACT evaluated aspects		Average
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?		4
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?		7
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?		5,5
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?		6,5
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?		7
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuations?		6,5

Figure 4 - Feasibility-impact results: Use of data redundancy strategies

CO.WP6-4: Dynamic resource management, such as network and security capabilities		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of Software Defined Network (SDN) will give new ways to design, build and operate the Valkyries network. By using SDNs the network is abstracted onto software, providing more benefits	The implementation is very feasible in terms of available technology. However, it's feasible to get down, so it is necessary to establish common standards at the EU level between all countries to have the same features for the SDNs. Consequently, the time for implementation and validation is

CO.WP6-4: Dynamic resource management, such as network and security capabilities		
	including flexibility, scalability, redundancy, and performance. Moreover, hardware is not a limitation since an administrator can add virtual hardware in the network.	higher than one year, being superior to the time of the Valkyries project.
Rating	6,2	5,9

Table 9 – CO.WP6-4: Dynamic resource management, such as network and security capabilities

Figure 5 - Feasibility-impact results: Dynamic resource management, such as network and security capabilities

CO.WP6-5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of this opportunity will improve Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training of different groups of First Responders who will acquire basic knowledge and practical skills for performing life-saving activities in various types of trauma and medical conditions in case of cross-border MCI.	This opportunity envisages creation of a Training kit for first responses to include curriculum, methodology and manual for joint multinational training in case of MCI. This training kit will build on some existing training materials used by first aid responders in the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy and the VALKYRIES partners. It will include online and on-site training for first responders how to use the VALKYRIES solutions for triage, wearables, etc. The implementation of the opportunity and the testing in the UCSs is comparatively easy and it can be done in the time frame of VALKYRIES project. The evaluation will be done by feedback questionnaire.
Rating	6,4	5,8

Table 10 – CO.WP6-5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses

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Figure 6 - Feasibility-impact results: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses

CO.WP6-6 Creation of an EU system for Lessons learned and exercises for first aid responses		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of this opportunity is related to creation of a Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) Lessons Learnt data base at the European level. This global database of lessons learned would connect outcomes that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement. The opportunity is with high impact on the improved cooperation, education and training for first aid responses in case of cross-border MCI.	Despite the existing UCPM Lessons Learnt initiative, the process of creation of Lessons Learnt data base at the European level requires coordinated and long-term efforts of the EU Member States. Besides, this process will require development of normative basis and procedures for data collection, storage and analysis. Therefore, despite the comparatively high impact, it is not feasible to implement this opportunity in the timeframe of VALKYRIES project and cannot be tested and validated during the Use Cases.
Rating	6,4	5,8

Table 11 – CO.WP6-6: Creation of an EU system for Lessons learned and exercises for first aid responses

Figure 7 - Feasibility-impact results: Creation of an EU system for Lessons learned and exercises for first aid responses

CO.WP6-7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	VOSTs are support units in disaster management that can generate additional information	This opportunity does not mean the creation of VOSTs, but the use of VOSTs and support and exploitation of VOSTs. It

CO.WP6-7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)		
	for crisis teams, decision-makers (Incident Commanders). The impact of this opportunity is that VOSTs can also be supportive and assist the authority in communicating through its own network. Those teams are networked within Europe (in some countries) and worldwide.	is possible to implement this opportunity, however the process of exploitation and continuing work of VOSTs between countries requires more time (this can take few years to harmonize the work of VOSTs). There will be discussion-based evaluation of this opportunity.
Rating	6,4	6,1

Table 12 – CO.WP6-7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

Figure 8 - Feasibility-impact results: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

CO.WP6-8: Development and implementation of a Strategy for rising of public awareness in MCI with catalogue of visual warning signs to alert and inform the population		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of this opportunity would be a creation of “local-municipal” portal which includes a development and updates on regular basis. The portal would give a complete picture of the citizens who live in the area, but also whether they have any expertise in a field that can contribute to an emergency. The Strategy would also include a catalogue of visual warning signs to alert and inform the population.	This opportunity represents a creation of a portal to gather a complete picture of citizens and catalogue of visual warning signs. The first part of the Strategy for rising of public awareness – creation of a portal would be feasible, but the second part – catalogue would be a big challenge. The use of a unified common language for several countries does not seem possible in many cases, the analysis of the signalling and citizen information systems used in each country of the European Union gains a great importance. This opportunity is not feasible to be implemented in the timeframe of VALKYRIES project.
Rating	6,1	5,8

Table 13 – CO.WP6-8: Development and implementation of a Strategy for rising of public awareness in MCI with catalogue of visual warning signs to alert and inform the population

Doc title: Roadmap for enhancing the Pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

Figure 9 - Feasibility-impact results: Development and implementation of a Strategy for rising of public awareness in MCI with catalogue of visual warning signs to alert and inform the population

CO.WP6-9 Implementation of Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	In most EU countries, the armed forces do not participate in the process of joint training and preparation according to common scenarios, common standards and procedures for planning and building disaster response capabilities. There is no sharing of training activities or exercises to facilitate the integration of institutions.	At the EU level, the Joint Allied Doctrine for Military Contribution to Humanitarian Aid has been agreed and approved among EU Member States. This doctrine provides basic guidance and standards for planning and executing operations in support of civil structures. The application of this doctrine in individual EU Member States would facilitate a homogeneous system of civil-military cooperation. There exists also a NATO CIMIC Centre of Excellence (in Hague, also member of the European Security Defence College) which can provide formal training in cooperation with the EU.
Rating	6,2	5,2

Table 14 – CO.WP6-9: Implementation of Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian

Figure 10 - Feasibility-impact results: Implementation of Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian

CO.WP6-10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	If this opportunity is realized, it will improve the joint	To realize this opportunity, it is envisaged to create a curriculum, methodology and

CO.WP6-10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions		
	<p>multinational civil-military training of various representatives engaged in actions in the defeat zone and emergency situations. This will help them use joint civil-military capabilities to perform activities at various cross-border MCIs.</p>	<p>guidance with procedures, steps and technics for joint multinational civil-military training in the case of emergencies. This training package will aim to build knowledge, skills and competencies for civil-military interaction and general first aid capabilities in EU countries.</p> <p>The training course is expected to last three days, be certified by the CIMIC Centre Of Excellence and be held at the European Security and Defence College. Implementing the capability and testing in Use Cases is relatively easy and can be done within the VALKYRIES project. Evaluation will be done through a feedback questionnaire.</p>
Rating	6,4	5,3

Table 15 – CO.WP6-10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

Figure 11 - Feasibility-impact results: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

CO.WP6-11 Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	<p>The implementation of this opportunity would be a creation of a minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and employees in the operational fields for supporting the professional first response teams. The aid of volunteers in case of MCI is fundamental but it is also very important that volunteers are always safe and useful for professional first aid teams.</p>	<p>At the EU level there are no existing specific training courses. To implement this opportunity, the purpose is to create a definition of a minimum set of competencies and skills to be acquired to be effective and safe in case of cross-border MCI. It will include online and on-site training for first responders about collaboration with other partners (first aid responders, civil-military capabilities etc.). Finally, a European database of volunteers skilled can be created.</p>

CO.WP6-11 Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

Rating	6,9	6,3
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Table 16 – CO.WP6-11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

FEASIBILITY evaluated aspects	Average
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?	7
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?	5,5
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?	7
Is there technology available to fulfill this opportunity?	8
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?	5
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?	5
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal? VERY IMPORTANT FOR 7.4	6,5

IMPACT evaluated aspects	Average
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?	5
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?	8
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?	7
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?	8
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?	8
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuations?	8

Figure 12 - Feasibility-impact results: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

6.2. Opportunities matrix

As soon as all clustered opportunities have been assessed, these were fit in the feasibility-impact matrix according to its feasibility-impact score (Figure 13).

As it can be seen in that figure, the differences among the scores are small which makes the selection of top 5 difficult. Nevertheless, two of the opportunities fall in the “quick wins” quadrant. Besides, one is in the opportunity in in the quadrant with high feasibility and comparatively high impact. Finally, other two are in the middle of the diagram with moderate impact and feasibility.

Figure 13 – WP6 clustered opportunities feasibility-impact matrix

In addition, Figure 14 represents the same graph as before, however, it presents the 5 top-ranked opportunities that, after consultation with the VALKYRIES WP6 partners, were chosen

afterwards to be implemented. The selected for implementation harmonisation opportunities are marked in green, while the rest are in red colour.

Figure 14 – Selected WP6 clustered opportunities feasibility-impact matrix

Finally, to get the total score of each opportunity, its feasibility score and its impact score have been added.

The following table shows the final feasibility-impact ranking with the partial and total scores obtained by each clustered opportunity proposed in WP6.

Order	Cl. opp code	Clustered opportunity name	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
1	CO.WP6-1	Common resource federation strategy	6.1	5.9	12.00
2	CO.WP6-2	Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	5.9	6.7	12.56
3	CO.WP6-3	Use of data redundancy strategies	5.7	6.0	11.64
4	CO.WP6-4	Dynamic resource management, such as network and security capabilities	6.2	5.9	12.12
5	CO.WP6-5	Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses	5.8	5.9	11.77
6	CO.WP6-6	Creation of an EU system for Lessons learned and exercises for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)	6.4	5.8	12.18
7	CO.WP6-7	Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTS)	6.4	6.1	12.45
8	CO.WP6-8	Development and implementation of a Strategy for rising of public awareness in MCI with catalogue of visual warning signs to alert and inform the population	6.1	5.8	11.88

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Order	Cl. opp code	Clustered opportunity name	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
9	CO.WP6-9	Implementation of Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance	6.2	5.2	11.43
10	CO.WP6-10	Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions	6.4	5.3	11.67
11	CO.WP6-11	Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities.	6.9	6.3	13.22

Table 17 – Final WP6 clustered opportunities ranking

7. Opportunities ranking

As a result of the scoring of each harmonisation opportunity based on its feasibility and impact, we continued with ranking the selected opportunities according to their score. Having in mind the time of execution of VALKYRIES project until September 2023, and after consultation with WP6 partners, we considered most reasonable to implement the 5 top-ranked clustered opportunities. The selected opportunities are presented in the table below (Table 18).

Order	Opportunity ranking in WP6	Total score
1 ^o	CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities.	13.22
2 ^o	CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	12.55
3 ^o	CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)	12.45
4 ^o	CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).	11.77
5 ^o	CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions	11.67

Table 18 – Opportunity ranking in WP6.

8. Identify interdependences

As an interdependence, we consider "the condition of two or more things depending on each other" as the Cambridge Dictionary defines it. This condition can easily be identified in the opportunities of WP6.

More specifically, interdependences were identified both within the opportunities of the WP6 and between different work packages as well. The following sections analyse this interdependence condition.

8.1 Inside of the WP6

Table 19 shows the interdependence of the WP6 opportunities.

Opportunity	Interdependences				
	CO.WP6.11	CO.WP6.12	CO.WP6.7	CO.WP6.5	CO.WP6.10
CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities.				X	X
CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data					
CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)					
CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).	X				X
CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions	X			X	

Table 19 – Dependency between opportunities within WP6

Figure 15 summarises graphically the interdependence between the opportunities within the WP6. A detailed description of the interdependence is described below.

Figure 15 – Interdependences within WP6

8.1.1 CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

This opportunity has interdependence with WP6 opportunity CO.WP6.5: Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual) and CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions.

8.1.2 CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

In this opportunity there are no interdependences with respect to the other WP6 opportunities. This means that it does not depend on any of the other opportunities to carry out the opportunity.

8.1.3 CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

There are no interdependences with this opportunity to the other WP6 opportunities. This means that implementation of this opportunity is not dependent on any other opportunity within WP6.

8.1.4 CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

This opportunity has interdependence with WP6 opportunity CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with

adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities and CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions, as far as it includes training also of volunteers and first responders, both military and civilians.

8.1.5 CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

This opportunity has interdependences to some extent with two other WP6 opportunities. The implementation of the option will depend on the implementation of the opportunities CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities and CO.WP6.5: Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses.

8.2. Between the WPs

Figure 16 summarises graphically the dependency between the opportunities with WP4 and WP5 that are detailed in the following subchapters.

Figure 16 – Interdependencies of WP6 with WP4 and WP5

8.2.1. CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities.

This opportunity has no interdependences with WP4 opportunities but has interdependencies with WP5 opportunities:

CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response. The competencies and skills to be defined should be described in standardised terminology to facilitate understanding and standardise training and education programmes.

CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans, CO.WP5-7 Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response plans and CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response. The establishing a minimum set of competencies and skills and integrating them into procedures will facilitate the harmonisation of all plans and procedures that may be activated in the event of an emergency.

8.2.2. CO.WP6.2 Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

Just as we have not identified any interdependences with the other opportunities in WP6, we have not identified any dependencies with the opportunities in WP4 and WP5. This is summarized in that we do not depend on any of the prioritized opportunities to perform cryptographic mechanism on the data.

8.2.3. CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

This opportunity has interdependences with WP4 opportunities:

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace – as VOSTs are in many cases groups of virtual volunteers working and monitoring the social media content during disasters, their cooperation and coordination interface with other national and international teams by establishing technical and collaborative frameworks to enable cooperation.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges – exchange of information is done mainly in digital form – mainly when we take into consideration that the exchange of information in between international teams. This reduces voice communication and leads to communication via visualisation, geo-localization and spatial analysis using geographic information systems.

Other interdependences of this opportunity are with WP5 opportunities:

CO.WP5-1 Standardization of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response – requirement for standardized terms in all phases of emergency management cycle is crucial and VOSTs operating in virtual space should be aware of these standardized terminology

CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response – VOSTs gather information from social networks (inputs and outputs) and this process requires standardization of shared information

CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response – All the inputs and outputs from VOSTs need to pass through the common federated system for sharing information in emergency response.

Establish a system of detection, management and dissemination of information for emergency preparedness, prevention and response harmonized at European level that considers the different realities and needs of its member states.

Reception and management of all information related to hoaxes and false news generated by member states with automatic notification to those affected.

Enhance synergies with other existing independent information collection and monitoring systems (VOST Europe, Copernicus) encourage the notification of hoaxes and fake news by those responsible for both public and private media, with special attention to social networks.

8.2.4. CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

This opportunity has interdependences with other WP4 opportunities: CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles, CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace and CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage as far as the training kit will include online and on-site training for first responders to use the VALKYRIES tools for triage, data exchange and wearables.

Also, it has direct interdependences with the WP5 opportunities:

CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response. All documentation developed for first aid education and training should use standardised terms, so that trained personnel use terminology from the outset that allows them to interoperate with other agencies regardless of where the emergency occurs

CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans, CO.WP5-7 Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response plans and CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response. The plans and procedures that are activated to respond to an emergency in all its phases must be implemented, which involves dissemination, education, training and coaching at different levels (population, first responders etc.).

8.2.5. CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

This opportunity has no interdependences with other WP4 ones, but it has a direct interdependencies with some of the WP5 opportunities:

CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response. Common procedures and standards developed for civil-military cooperation should use standardised terms in their development, which will facilitate their understanding as well as coordination and interoperability in case of an emergency.

CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans, CO.WP5-7 Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response plans and CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response. Civil-military cooperation and how it should be carried out should be reflected in the plans and procedures that are activated in response to an emergency. Successful participation of the armed forces in civil emergencies can only be achieved if they are integrated into the civil protection system, which requires procedures and standards that regulate the training and their actions.

9. Evaluation in short of top ranked opportunities

Tables 20 to 24 present a short description of the top five ranked harmonisation opportunities in WP6.

CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

Why	At the EU level there are no existing specific training courses but to implement this opportunity, the purpose is to create a definition of minimum set of competencies and skills to be acquired for volunteers involved in the operational fields for supporting the professional first response teams. The goal is to be effective and safe in case of cross-border MCI. It will include online and on-site training for first responders about collaboration with other partners (first aid responders, civil-military capabilities etc.). Finally, a European database of volunteers skilled can be created.
How	Main steps to implement the opportunity: Definition of a minimum set of competence and skills that volunteers should acquire to be effective and safe in case of cross-border MCI; development of curriculum and education methodology (online and on-site training). Close collaboration with similar opportunities to be aligned (first aid responders, civil-military capabilities etc.); creation of a European database of volunteers skilled. Testing of the competencies during the Use Cases (UCs) implementation.

Table 20 - Opportunity CO.WP6.11 evaluation

CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

Why	The main problem regarding the mechanisms to provide data confidentiality relies in their computational capabilities. This includes the capabilities required to encrypt the data, to decrypt the data and the capabilities necessary to venerate a certain cryptosystem.
How	Main steps to implement the opportunity: Application of light cryptographic mechanisms that can be used during the emergency situations; Encrypt the data within the database, when applicable; Mostly making use of secure protocols such as HTTPS for data transmission. The thrust nature of the Valkyries requires users' roles to be mapped and assigned by each entity tool.

Table 21 – Evaluation of CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data.

CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

Why	VOSTs operate in some countries in Europe and worldwide. In Europe, VOST Europe was created as an umbrella organisation for European VOSTs, and to support the creation of new national/regional VOSTs and participate in Pan-European activities. The original strategy included being sustainable, multi-national and multi-language. The aim is to implement the use of VOSTs in UC2.
How	Main steps to implement the opportunity: We are going to implement this opportunity during the execution of UC2 on 2 levels. 1 st level will be implemented via discussion with all participating responders. The work of VOSTs in different EU countries will be presented as their role during extraordinary incidents. Practical use and importance of this

CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

	<p>activity will be confirmed via a questionnaire. Despite the execution of UC2, no VOSTs representatives will be present, and this activity will not be included directly in the exercise, the need for its validity check will be confirmed via discussion/questionnaire with end users.</p> <p>2nd level will be implemented during the execution of UC2 and output from VOST will be included into the information flow. Staff managing the incident will have to evaluate this information and take appropriate actions.</p>
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*Table 22 – Opportunity CO.WP6.7 evaluation.***CO.WP6.5: Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)**

Why	<p>Currently, in most cases, training for first aid responses is done separately for medical teams and other first responders (civil protection, firefighters, police, military, volunteers, etc.). Besides, most of the courses are thought at the national level. Finally, there is a lack of training on how first responders use advanced technological solutions to improve the effectiveness of their work to get there ere is a clear need to train first responders together both at national and international levels.</p>
How	<p>Main steps to implement the opportunity:</p> <p>We are going to suggest Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training of different groups of First Responders (FR) who need to acquire basic knowledge and practical skills for performing life-saving activities in various types of trauma and medical conditions in case of cross-border MCI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define student profile; • Create basic training for the drill by disaster experts; • Evaluation with tests before and after the training in level of competences acquired; • Surveys of satisfaction and self-perception of the students of the competences acquired with the training; • Evaluation of the training acquired at the level of knowledge and practice with check list.

*Table 23 – Opportunity CO.WP6.5 evaluation.***CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions**

Why	<p>Civilian and military teams use different rules, procedures and standards when providing emergency assistance in different EU countries. This creates problems in communication, interaction and coordination between them. As usual, the courses are held at the national level. There is a definite lack of joint training for military and civilian emergency responders to improve the effectiveness of their work and to effectively respond together both nationally and internationally. This is the way to build joint capabilities for Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) in case of various types of emergencies.</p>
How	<p>Main steps to implement the opportunity:</p> <p>Joint training programs and scenarios for civil-military teams should be developed to enable mutual understanding and build common emergency response capabilities. The main steps are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define student's profile; • Create basic training curricula for the drill by civil and military experts;

CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Evaluation with tests before and after the training in level of competences acquired;• Surveys of satisfaction and self-perception of the students of the competences acquired with the training;• Evaluation of the training acquired at the level of knowledge and practice with check list.

Table 24 – Opportunity CO.WP6.10 evaluation.

10. Roadmap for pre-standardisation

10.1 WP6 Roadmap

At the WP6 level three out of five harmonization opportunities look like most interdependent. Those are CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities; CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual) and CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions. This is logical as far as all three are related to improving education and training of first aid responders, including volunteers. The other two opportunities CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data and CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) are related to improving/securing data exchange and enhancing collaboration among first responders.

When the interrelations among WP6, WP5 and WP4 harmonisation opportunities are analysed, the situation is close. Only the opportunity CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) looks like more interrelated.

The described situation of interdependences cannot be used as a basis for identification which opportunity is more important to be included in the harmonisation roadmap of WP6. As a team, we decided that all of them are with high impact and feasibility, and therefore we would suggest separate roadmaps for each opportunity.

10.2. Opportunity Roadmap

10.2.1. CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

The following figure shows a proposed roadmap to achieve a pre-standardization of minimum set of competences and skills for volunteers into the field operational procedures and their required training.

Minimum set of competences and skills for volunteers in field operation

Figure 17 - Roadmap of the opportunity CO.WP6.11 – Minimum set of competences and skills for volunteers in field operation

10.2.1.1. Demonstration in VALKYRIES (September 2023):

Identifying a minimum set of competencies for the volunteers according with other similar opportunities and tasks concerning FRs in multi casualties and then organise a multidisciplinary training course for different groups of First Responders is the first step to be addressed. These competencies will enable volunteers to acquire practical skills to be useful to other actors and also to be within the activities of the emergency management. Giving and guarantying a common competence for volunteers will speed their incorporation within the workflow dealing with the emergency and it would minimise the difficulties arising from an incident on cross-border territory. A proposal of these competences and their training is implemented and tested in the use cases of the VALKYRIES Project. The outcome and lessons learned derived from the VALKYRIES could be used as starting point to continue with the pre-standardisation process.

10.2.1.2. Create Working Group and scientific publications (September 2023 – September 2024):

The next step is the dissemination of the results among the academic community to have a discussion and improvement of the output. This will provide the endorsement that our outcome is applicable to solve the identified problem: minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field.

To address this discussion, we suggest the creation of a specific Working Group that could observe the VALKYRIES output, orient and decide the best approach on this matter. This process involves the creation of different scientific papers and their successive publication in specialised peer-reviewed journals. It is important the involvement of volunteer's organizations and other important stakeholders like Civil Protection authorities or first aid responders to obtain a relevant consent. With the acceptance of the academic community the pre-standardisation process can move forward.

10.2.1.3. Consensus at National level (September 2024 – September 2026):

With the acceptance by the academic community and relevant stakeholder organizations, the next step is to promote the use of the results by some volunteer's organisations and organisms involved in emergency management within specific areas to test the training program and get feedback for continuous improvement process and sustainability.

The development of a legal frameworks at national level is fundamental to guarantee the integration of volunteers into Civil Protection system (insurances scheme, roles and responsibilities and procedures).

When successful and relevant results are obtained at a national level, this can be promoted to other countries.

10.2.1.4. Consensus at EU level (September 2026 – September 2028):

After debugging the process within one country, the outcome should be validated in other countries, involving them in using these results and training, especially in the case of cross-border MCI. EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) exercises could be used for this purpose. Using the same harmonised competencies and skills for volunteers in different countries will make easier and faster the use of foreign volunteers in cross-border areas with a large-scale emergency when local resources could be limited and allow systematic integration without country/local dependency. When several countries have tested and validated the results, it can be considered that the training and competences are accepted by the academic community and the practitioners and can be extended to cover the EU harmonization policy and practices.

10.2.1.5. Promote EU Legal Framework (After September 2028):

The final step should be to contact the standardising EU entity for the EU MS with a request for EU standardisation policy / guidelines.

The Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (DG-ECHO) through EUCPM carries out actions to support, coordinate and supplement the actions of the Member States. EUCPM could push for proposing guidelines/best practises in a standard way within Europe to cooperate effectively with volunteers as actors in emergency management, updating the EU legal framework accordingly.

10.2.2. CO.WP6.2 Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

Figure 18 shows the steps identified which must be performed to achieve a pre-standardization of this opportunity. Subsequently, all these steps which compose the roadmap are explained below.

Figure 18 - Roadmap of the opportunity CO.WP6.2 - Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data.

10.2.2.1. Demonstration in VALKYRIES (September 2023 – December 23):

The first step of a pre-standardisation is to obtain what we want to pre-standardise, in our case the cryptographic methods to protect information in emergency situations. These mechanisms will be implemented and demonstrated in the use cases of the VALKYRIES Project, once they have been demonstrated we will have these cryptographic methods validated and we will be able to continue with the process. This is a very important step, as it is the first one, which consists of the design and implementation that we will be dragging along throughout this long process. The secure protocols adopted to the demo will be implemented and tests in a simulated event running in a real-world scenario, which will allow for the identification of potential pitfalls, performances and limitations. These outcomes can be used to support potential improvements and consolidate the technology.

10.2.2.2. Analysis of the results obtained during the demonstration (January 2024 – June 2024)

Once the demonstration is finished, the next step consists of studying if the implemented cryptographic mechanisms have been able to success the needs of the project from the results achieved in the demo based on some metrics. Otherwise, it would be necessary to study other technics which are already available in the literature and could be standardised. Subsequently, we should have to validate the new ones implemented by internal demonstration (using a real scenario or simulated) before try to pre-standardise this opportunity.

10.2.2.3. Several scientific publications (July 2024 – December 2024)

The next step to carry out any pre-standardisation is the acceptance of these data protection mechanisms by the scientific community. This process is based on the fact that, by being accepted by this type of community, they provide our "product" with validity as they would pass review processes by highly prestigious scientists. This step will be carried out by writing and presenting different scientific articles with the design, implementation and tests that we have carried out using these types of cryptographies in different simulations or emergency situations.

10.2.2.4. Define consensus in a country (January 2025 – June 2025)

Once we have the acceptance of such a prestigious community as the scientific community, we will be able to take these mechanisms to bodies and organisations so that they can add these methods. This will be a first step towards harmonisation. Once we have functional and secure cryptographic mechanisms, they should be used by bodies so that they can understand and ratify their benefits.

10.2.2.5. Define consensus in EU (July 2025 – June 2026):

When a company, country, etc. has incorporated these protection mechanisms in its functions, particularly in emergency situations, we must ensure that these mechanisms are used by other countries, companies, etc. That is why we will seek to harmonise these mechanisms within such an important body as the European Union, so that its use will be recommended by the European Union for the use of the associated countries. In this way we will be achieving the much-needed harmonisation.

10.2.2.6. Request standardisation (July 2026 – On going):

Finally, once these mechanisms have been adopted by the European Union, the last remaining step will be the drafting and submission of the standardisation application to the relevant body.

10.2.3. CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

The following figure synthesises the main steps proposed to achieve a pre-standardization of this opportunity, and the details of each step are described below.

Figure 19 - Roadmap of the opportunity CO.WP6.7 - Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

10.2.3.1. Demonstration in VALKYRIES (June 2023)

VOSTs represents modern activity. Current status is that such units already exist in some EU countries as well as there exists EU umbrella organization also. Standardization of these activities is covered. Open points are the countries/regions where such teams are not on place, respectively collaboration and improvements of existing ones. First step of creating a pre-standardisation map is the description of existing units, how they were established and how they are working. Subsequently research on ongoing initiatives of establishing these teams would be prepared with aim to enlarge network of VOSTs.

From the point of view of standardization, it is necessary to follow processes of existing teams, to prepare and disseminate mainly the descriptions of how they work and what are the results in case of extraordinary situation. How these outputs can be shared, displayed/interpreted and used with responders on different levels.

Within the VALKYRIES project, there is no space to solve this issue comprehensively, but the part of use of information coming from VOST can be tested, as well as possible way how to present such an information within related communication tool. This will be a case of UC2 and proposed reference integration (SIGRUN). After this phase it will be possible to confirm importance of this opportunity and formulate next steps with the pre-standardisation process.

10.2.3.2. Dissemination and involvement of key stakeholders (October 2023 – September 2024)

The output of VALKYRIES should be presented and disseminated to key stakeholders as VOSTs organisations, First Responders in MCI, EENA 112 (Social Media in Emergency Management group) and researchers from Social Media-Driven Disaster Risk Management Task Force. The aim of dissemination will be gathering recommendations for improvement and the acceptance of the community.

10.2.3.3. Define consensus in a country (October 2024 – September 2026)

The standardisation of the use of VOST within the emergency cycle requires that they are able to provide additional value-added information at the emergency COP without requiring additional work from those involved. SIGRUN can help in achieving this. The next step after VALKYRIES output and community discussion should develop tools to automatise the exchange information within an emergency ecosystem.

VOST Portugal leads the technological development of open-source solutions that are available to other VOST in Europe, and they are currently using CONFIRM¹ (CrOwd maNagement platForm for Disaster Risk Management) tool to manage the information from the media. Developing a tool to enter relevant data from VOST to VALKYRIES reference integration / connector to extract data from CONFIRM application to VALKYRIES ecosystem could make easier the validation and acceptance of the VOST contribution to the COP. Part of the information of the COP could be available to VOST in order to support the social media accounts of the emergency services.

Taking advantage of the several VOSTs already present in Europe, this test could be done in at National level. Legal framework is basic to guarantee the integration of this virtual volunteers into Civil Protection system.

10.2.3.4. Define consensus in the EU (October 2026 – September 2028)

After a successful experience at the national level, VOST Europe should encourage other VOSTs in Europe to adopt the same criteria to standardise their collaboration within their country, following similar procedures adapted to the specific requirements and legal framework on each country. A positive outcome within the emergency cycle would encourage the creation of new VOSTs. VOST Europe should implement mutual exercises, best practice exchange and information sharing. Joint actions and cooperation will ensure sustainability, standardization and harmonization.

10.2.3.5. Request standardisation (After October 2028)

As in the case of volunteers, VOSTs are trusted agents supporting Civil Protection authorities. VOST Europe should be present within the EUCPM, as an emergency agency, participating in its training/exercise programme, and it will be the EUCPM that will push to propose guidelines/best practices in a standard way within Europe to cooperate effectively with VOST as actors in emergency management, updating the EU legal framework accordingly.

¹ <https://vosteuropa.org/confirm/>

10.2.4. CO.WP6.5: Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

The following figure summarises the main steps proposed to achieve a pre-standardization of this opportunity. The details of each step in pre-standardisation is described in the text below.

Figure 20 - Roadmap of the opportunity CO.WP6.5 - Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

10.2.4.1. Demonstration in VALKYRIES use cases (May - October 2023)

The first step of a pre-standardisation map is to develop a Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training course for different groups of FRs (firefighters, police officers, military personnel, civil protection practitioners, NGOs, volunteers, etc.) who will acquire basic knowledge and practical skills for performing life-saving activities in various types of trauma and medical conditions at the scene of accidents occurring in cross-border areas with multiple casualties.

This training will be implemented and demonstrated in the use cases of the VALKYRIES Project. After it has been demonstrated, we will have the training validated, then we will be able to continue with the pre-standardisation process.

Within the VALKYRIES project scope (UCs execution), the training is focused on a specific area (training of first responders on how to use innovative VALKYRIES technological solutions for

digitalising triage, improved situational awareness), but the standardization process should be the same in other specific areas.

10.2.4.2. Development of several scientific publications (October 2023 – September 2024):

The next step to be fulfilled when the Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training for FRs is validated, is the dissemination of the results among the academic community, critical discussion and improvement. The permanent working group European Committee for First Aid Education (EC First Aid) would be a potential stakeholder to be involved with. This critical review and possible acceptance by the academic community will give us the endorsement that this training is accurate, adequate and applicable to solve the identified problem, namely the gap in joint, multinational and multidisciplinary training for first aid responses. This process continues with the creation of different scientific articles/papers and their successive publication in specialised peer-reviewed journals. As soon as these academic publications are accepted and published, we can steadily concern our training can undergo the process of pre-standardization.

10.2.4.3. Define consensus in a country (October 2024 – September 2026)

As soon as we have the acceptance of the academic community, we must get our product (Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training course for FRs) to be used by some practitioners in first responder organizations (firefighters, police officers, military personnel, civil protection practitioners, NGOs, volunteers, etc.). When we accomplish this trial and we are sure that our training course is used in several first responders' organizations at a country level, we can achieve first step in pre-harmonization, i.e., the training course is used by the specialized organisation in the country as a good practice.

10.2.4.4. Define consensus in the EU (October 2026 – September 2028)

When we have this harmonization or the use of the Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training course for FRs by one country, we will try to get involved more EU Member States, to use this training in case of cross-border MCI. This step will be a very important endeavour in the pre-standardization roadmap because the training was already accepted by the academic community and the practitioners, and it will expand the coverage of the EU harmonization policy and practices.

10.2.4.5. Request standardisation (After October 2028)

Finally, once the Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training course for FRs has being used by many first responders' organizations in many countries and has been validated, we will proceed to contact the standardising EU entity for the EU Member States with a request for standardisation (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work and the).

Promote the creation of a validated European Training Course for all disaster medicine responders that includes:

- Education and training in disaster medicine;
- Education and training in command-and-control Preparedness and management of emergencies, multi-casualty incidents and disasters;
- Training for trainers;
- Analysis of simulation data. Analyse the impact of training on students and explore areas for improvement. Promote research to create a validated system of education and training, reproducible anywhere in the world.

To facilitate dissemination, trainers in each country will translate the content into other languages and report the results to a central headquarters for analysis at the multinational and multi-Centre levels.

10.2.5. CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

The proposed roadmap to address and implement this opportunity is represented in the following figure:

Figure 21 - Roadmap of the opportunity CO.WP6.10 - Using common procedures and standards for training and civil military actions

10.2.5.1. Demonstration in VALKYRIES (June - October 2023)

The first step in the process is to examine who will be trained and why, what knowledge and skills should be acquired, in our case common procedures for actions between military and civilian teams in emergency situations. These knowledge, skills and procedures will be included in the curriculum of a three-day Joint Civil-Military training course offered under the VALKYRIES project, which will be demonstrated and tested, resulting in a validated methodology, program and professional framework.

10.2.5.2. Development of several scientific publications (June 2023 – September 2024):

The next step in the implementation of joint procedures and standards within the framework of civil-military cooperation is the acceptance of these procedures and standards by the scientific

community. Here we will bet on the fact that by justifying the need to improve the procedures and standards of civil-military interaction and presenting our steps for its implementation, they receive the approval of highly qualified specialists and scientists. This step will be carried out by writing and presenting various scientific papers with the rationale, content and guidelines for improving the joint training of military and civilian professionals to act in various emergency situations.

10.2.5.3. Define consensus in a country (October 2024 – September 2026)

Once we have the approval of such a prestigious community as the scientific one, we will be able to bring these mechanisms to bodies and organizations so that they can add these new capabilities. We will propose the developed methodology, training program and qualification framework of the Joint Civil-Military training course for discussion and certification before the Disaster Risk Reduction Council under the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria. This will be the first step towards harmonization. In addition, we will develop a Handbook/Guidance with steps, procedures and directions for joint civil-military interaction in case of different kind of emergencies. Once we have an approved methodology, program and professional framework, they must be put into practice and their benefits revealed and evaluated. When we accomplish this trial and we are sure that our training course is used in several organizations at a country level, we can achieve first step in pre-harmonization, i.e., the training course is used by the specialized organisation in the country as a good practice.

10.2.5.4. Define consensus in the EU (October 2026 – September 2028)

When this harmonization is in place and the use of the Joint Multinational and Civil-Military Training Course is approved by one country, we will attempt to involve more EU Member States to use this training in the event of a cross-border MCI. For this purpose, we will propose that the course be certified by the CIMIC COE in The Hague and, within the framework of the European Security and Defence College, start training military and civilian specialists from EU countries. This step will be a very important undertaking in the pre-standardisation road map as the training has already been accepted by the academic community and practitioners and will broaden the scope of EU harmonization policy and practice.

10.2.5.5. Request standardisation (After October 2028)

Finally, once the Joint Multinational Civil-Military Training Course has been used by many organizations in many countries and validated, we will continue to contact the EU standardization body for EU Member States with a request for standardization. European Security and Defence College will be essential in this stage.

11. Stake holder's evaluation

As in the WP4 and WP5, the main question asked to the members of the External Advisory Board (EAB) was "Do you consider that this aggregated opportunity presents a high impact and feasibility to be implemented in the EU?". As whole we received five filled out questionnaires.

The following paragraphs summarise the responses of the members of the EAB regarding each of the prioritised harmonisation opportunities that are candidates for demonstration and validation during the UCs and possible follow-on pre-harmonisation efforts.

CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities. The collected data from the members of the EAB shows general positive evaluations with some comments that it is important the volunteers to know their tasks and obligations, as well as those of the first responders and to collaborate in a way which guarantees successful implementation. Volunteers proved their effectiveness in many operations.

CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data in cross-border Multi Casualty Incidents (MCI) – Also general positive evaluations of the members of the EAB. Only one of them thinks that protection of sensitive data in MCI is an important topic but the feasibility of cryptographic mechanisms needs more discussions among experts to implement this opportunity at the EU level.

CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) in cross-border MCI

The level of support of the members of the EAB for the implementation of this harmonisation opportunity is comparatively lower and more diverse in comparison to the previous two. The responses are one “slightly agree”, two “agree”, one “no” and one expert declares “I can’t evaluate correctly the impact of such teams”. An example of a positive response is “If we understand the VOSTs as independent supranational teams that assume the advice and support of the professionals assigned to the command-and-control centres to manage the situation, that would be a very good help and this contribution would also be well received”.

CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses in cross-border MCI (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).

The support of the members of the EAB for this opportunity is high and there are not big differences among the responses. They are: one “strongly agree, two “fully agree” and one “agree. One of the experts is a bit sceptic: “I believe that these aspects are already quite developed at the present time. Another issue is that the appropriate and frequent training actions are being carried out for the participants not always with high quality. I don’t think there is much room for “inventing” new teaching methodologies”.

CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions in cross-border MCI

Most of the members of the EAB participating in the survey are positive regarding the impact and feasibility of this harmonisation opportunity. The responses are: “slightly agree” and three – “agree”. An example of a positive evaluation is the following “Yes, positive impact on both the military and civilians”. Again, one of the experts is sceptic “I believe that governments have tended to reduce military training for the civilian population in general and that this position conflicts with the approach of using common and standard procedures for training in civil-military actions. My opinion is that this type of joint training should be carried out between civilian and military personnel, especially in the different professionals involved in events such as those addressed in this project.”

Finally, we asked the members of the EAB two questions to identify their level of support for the map of certification for first responders and the harmonisation strategy suggested by VALKYRIES consortium. On both questions the experts give positive responses and underline the importance of the creation of common set of minimum competencies and joint training. Some examples are regarding the VALKYRIES map of certification: “The certification of the first

responders in not uniform between states. There should be some basic competencies common to all the operations groups and then some exclusive competencies for each group, although they should not be unknown to the rest. Training, study and simulation are very important to achieve an adequate, coordinated and effective response on the ground” and “I believe the map of certification is necessary in the future”.

Regarding the harmonisation strategy some examples of positive evaluations the underline the importance of the harmonisation efforts is: “I firmly believe that the harmonisation strategy is well oriented and will deliver results” and “Harmonisation process is always difficult one but any effort to achieve a common strategy must be considered as successful. So, I accept positively the results of VALKYRIES project in this direction.”

12. Conclusions

This section summarises conclusions from the analyses of the top five ranked opportunities.

12.1 Conclusions on CO.WP6.11 – Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities

Volunteers enable governments to extend their resources during MCI by providing them with services they could not otherwise afford. Nevertheless, their integration into Civil Protection systems should be in a systematic way. Providing them with a minimum set of competencies through specific, concrete and standardised training ensures efficient integration in cross-border emergencies.

It is important to have a clear and acknowledged role and responsibilities within the national system, to determine the minimum required competences and develop the curricula, training and certification methodology. Competence, skills, and curricula must be adapted to the risk and activity, and it should allow the fast integration of new staff (either with on-line training or quick in situ one for basic tasks).

National and cross-border exercises related to civil protection emergency management cycle should incorporate volunteers for sustainability and continuous improvement.

Civil protection authorities should recognise volunteers' organisations and integrate them into their operational framework to increase response capabilities, giving them a regulatory framework and an insurance policy to ensure an optimal protection of volunteers according to each national legislation.

Volunteers must be protected, and it is therefore the responsibility of the authorities to ensure that appropriate health and safety measures are implemented to prevent volunteers from being exposed to substances that may pose a health hazard through inadequate protection.

The steps to pre-standardise this integration of volunteers in the field operational procedures are common to other opportunities: the involvement of the academic community, to obtain consensus at national level and to increase the number of countries to obtain consensus at European level.

12.2. Conclusions on CO.WP6.2 - Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

The use of cryptographic mechanisms for the protection of the data stored during an emergency provides our system with a great capacity for protection against the threats that may arise in these situations. The protection given by our system by storing encrypted information makes our data secure in a very simple way as these mechanisms are already defined in the literature. To carry out this simple task, implement it and harmonise it in many countries, several previously defined steps must be followed.

These steps will ensure that our protection solution is adopted first by the scientific community and then by one country, two countries, etc., until a European consensus is reached on this issue, providing Europe with sufficient data protection in multi-victim emergency situations.

Finally, a standardisation process will have to be carried out, which takes a long time, but once this is achieved, a complete harmonisation will gradually take place. This harmonisation will result in the handling of these data and these mechanisms by all, and it will be easy to deal with them.

12.3. Conclusions on CO.WP6.7 - Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

In contemporary crisis management operations, both physical volunteers and particularly digital ones play an important role during an emergency. Even digital volunteers' role is increasingly relevant in MCI environment where information plays a key role.

A Virtual Operations Support Team, in accordance with emergency management cycle, is an attempt to make use of new communication technologies, social media tools, etc. so that a team of trusted agents (digital volunteers) can lean support via the internet to those on site who may be overwhelmed by the volume of data generated during a multi casualty incident.

Nowadays, most of the VOSTs are activated to perform specific functions in support of affected organisations. In Europe, there has been established VOST EUROPE which operates across Europe. In some countries, these special teams of digital experts have already worked in different ways. The aim of VOST EUROPE is to create a space for interexchange experiences, and best practices, mitigate common problems with common solutions, as well as to search for opportunities as representatives of digital volunteers. It is obvious that this opportunity does not cover or invent a new model of teams of digital volunteers/experts, but focuses more on the use of VOSTs, support effectiveness and utility for the work of responders in disaster. Standardisation of this opportunity is required, as VOSTs (those existing and properly working) have successfully supported emergency managers in handling an increasingly challenging media space during incident deployments. Based on individual skills and capabilities, VOSTs have helped to filter relevant information out of social media content, improved situational awareness of emergency managers and engaged actively with the public. Once VOSTs can operate at the national level with the purpose to help emergency managers/responders, then there is also space for make those teams work together at international level. Because at international level, VOSTs could become a central element of collaboration and cooperation for emergency management organisation and could actively communicate with public. Additionally, online word knows no boundaries. This could not happen without a clear commitment from governmental agencies. Support and integration of VOSTs into emergency management structures in each country would present standardisation process.

12.4. Conclusions on CO.WP6.5 - Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

The results from the analyses made in the framework of deliverables D6.5 and D6.6 revealed an important education and training capability gap and the need to develop, validate and pre-standardise a training kit for Joint multinational course for first aid responses.

The content of the training, the methodology and some examples of the training materials will be presented in D6.4. This will be a short 3-day training and only the most essential knowledge and skills of first responders will be covered that are necessary for the individual to provide first aid with a limited amount of equipment; to recognize the emergency, activate an EMS system

and serve as liaisons with other emergency services, fire brigade, military units, police; to recognize emergency conditions or the proper extent of injuries which require first aid; to administer appropriate first aid for life-threatening situations (relative to airway, breathing and circulation); to support the process of evacuation of the victim to a medical care facility; to assist health care providers, etc. Besides the basis medical knowledge and skills, the course will provide additional training for first responder's duties and responsibilities; medico-legal principles; GDPR and privacy-preserving related issues, data management and interoperability opportunities; communication skills and the teamwork; cross-cultural skills, etc.

The methodology for the teaching can be focused both on physical and on-line sessions.

The implementation of this opportunity is expected to improve first responder's preparedness to work effectively in case of cross-border MCI.

12.5. Conclusions on CO.WP6.10 - Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions.

The use of common procedures and standards for civil-military training will fill a very important gap in education and training capabilities. This includes the development, validation and preliminary standardization of a training kit for a joint multinational civil-military first aid response course. It is intended to be a short 3-day training to acquire the knowledge and skills of persons to respond jointly, to coordinate their efforts in an emergency situation, to act jointly with military structures and emergency services, fire, police and volunteers, to render first aid, assist the situation assessment process, conduct evacuation, etc.

The aim of the course is to provide knowledge about the duties and responsibilities of first responders, joint management of teams, introduce some principles of civil-military interaction, basic communication skills and teamwork, etc. The course can be conducted both on physical and through online platform.

It is also envisaged to develop a Handbook/Manual with steps, procedures and guidelines for joint Civil-Military Interaction (CMI) in case of various types of emergencies. In this way, a higher coordination of actions and synchronization of efforts between military and civilian teams in the emergency area will be achieved.

13. Annex A – References and bibliography

13.1 Internal references

1. VALKYRIES D1.7 - Consultation strategy
2. VALKYRIES D2.2 - Terminology and semantics
3. Valkyries D4.5 Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
4. Valkyries D4.6 Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
5. Valkyries D4.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
6. Valkyries D5.5 Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
7. Valkyries D5.6 Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
8. Valkyries D5.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
9. Valkyries D6.5 Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
10. Valkyries D6.6 Harmonization opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

14. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CIMIC	Civil-Military Cooperation
CIMIC COE	Civil-Military Cooperation Centre of Excellence
CMI	Civil-Military Interaction
CONFIRM	CrOwd maNagement platForm for dlsaster Risk Management
CP	Civil Protection
DG-ECHO	Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
EAB	External Advisory Group
EENA	European Emergency Number Association
EU	European Union
EUCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
FR	First Responders
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OP	Opportunity
SDN	Software Defined Network
TOC	Table of Content
UC	Use Case
VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams
WP	Work Package

Table 25 - Glossary